

British Paramountcy and Rajputana States: From Chamber of Princes to Round Table Conference (1921-1930)

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The Sovereignty of the British crown is supreme in India and therefore no ruler of an Indian State can justifiably claim to negotiate with the British Government on an equal footing. This supremacy was not based only upon treaties and engagements but that it existed in dependently of them."

- Lord Reading

The two important events occurred in the Constitutional history of India during the years 1919-1921 were of great significance. First, the introduction of the Montague-Chelmsford Reforms marked the beginning of the grant of responsible Government to the provinces. Secondly, the establishment of the Chamber of Princes as a forum of mutual consultations among the Princes was a step in breaking the age-long policy of isolation."¹

The matter in his note dated 2 February 1919 and forcefully argued the case of India for inclusion in the League. His note, however, was more or restricted to legal and constitutional aspect of the issue. Maharaja Ganga Singh supplemented this memorandum with a note of his wherein he justified the inclusion of India on Political and general grounds. The Maharaja contended that if people of India with their civilisation of untold antiquity were fit to fight in Europe side by side with other civilised this alone was a cogent point sufficiently warranting the inclusion of India in the League."² This conference was a prelude to the establishment of the Chamber of Princes.³

The formation of Chamber of Princes

With the end of the rule of the East India Company in 1858, the British Government adopted a new policy towards the Princely States. It as a dual policy of conciliation and friendship on the one hand and of systematic undermining their sovereign status on the other hand. The Princes were assured of the status quo. They were granted

the right of adoption by the Sanads issued to them. They were given various rewards for the services they rendered during uprising. But the course of political practices and economic development in India as a whole (which the British treated as one charge) also resulted in the curtailment of and infringements on their sovereignty."⁴

The constant interference in the internal affairs of their states by British Government was painful to the Princes but they were helpless. Because of the policy of keeping them isolated, the Princes were not in the position to make united efforts to get their grievances redressed. They problems. But during the uprising of 1857, it was felt that there should be were not permitted to talk or confer freely with each other on common native states. As a first step it was proposed in the proclamation of the a close rapport between the British Government and the Princes of the Queen in 1858 that an Imperial Privy Council consisting of few selected Princes and top British officers should be formed.⁵ The scheme, however, could not be implemented. Lord Lytton attempted to create a body of the Princes and prepared a tentative plan for an Indian Privy Council confined to and composed of the big chiefs to discuss common interest."⁶ The plan was not accepted by the Home Government on the ground that 'it might give rise to common understanding to Princes and united pressure such as might embarrass the Government of India.'

Lord Curzon's plan for the formation of a council of ruling Princes had also brushed aside; and Lord Minto's subsequent scheme for an advisory council of rulers and big land holders to combat political discontent had met with the same fate. But during the Viceroyalties of Lord Hardinge and Lord Chelmsford, conferences of Rulers became a regular feature. The joint authors suggested these ad hoc conferences should be replaced by a permanent body known as the Council of Princes, which would give the rulers the opportunity of informing the government as to their sentiments and wishes, of broadening their outlook and of conferring with one another and with the Government."⁷

In its place a purely honorific body known as the Councillors of the Empress came into existence.⁸ A similar scheme for the formation of the Council of Princes was taken up by Lord Curzon but that too was not favoured by His Majesty's Government. Lord Minto's suggestion for an advisory council of Rulers and big landlords for combating the political unrest prevailing at the time met the same fate. But they certainly tended to mould the trend of thinking on the subject.⁹

The Princes were keen to obtain avowal in an explicit manner from the Government of India for their direct relationship with the Crown so as to provide security to their internal sovereignty. The British Government was also keen to seek mutual co-operation and help from the princely states in suppressing seditious and anti British activities in India. This identity of interest laid the foundation of the new British policy towards princely states based on mutual trust, co-operation and friendship. In 1913, and again in 1914, Lord Hardinge invited some of the Princes to confer with him on the question of education, a subject of vital interest for the princely order.

Maharaja Ganga Singh of Bikaner, the doyen among the Princes and an elder statesman of the British Empire, took up the thread of earlier princely states. He was keenly interested in having a close association of efforts. He was a strong advocate of the internal sovereignty of the Princes with the Government of India. For achieving this end he was for a permanent organisation or a common forum where the Princes could gather together and ventilate their grievances collectively and exchange Co-operation between the Government of India and the princely states, views on matters concerning their states.¹⁰ Ganga Singh, who was for close started working strenuously for giving a practical shape to this idea.

In January 1914, the Maharaja submitted a minute to the Viceroy arguing for the creation of the some sort of machinery which would secure sustained and intimate co-operation between 'the two India's'. His main emphasis in the minute was that the ruling chiefs should, as the representatives and heads of their states, have some formal part in the Government of the Empire. They have a right, in view of their partnership in and their contributions to the defence of the Empire, to be heard in regard to the matters of Imperial interest and they also desire to have an opportunity for mutual consultation and discussions on matters affecting their own order. These views were received with sympathetic attitude by the Viceroy, who in his concluding remarks of his address to the Chief's college conference held in Delhi on 3 March 1914, stated that he would seek collective opinion of the Princes whenever possible on matters affecting the interests of their order.¹¹

The inauguration of the 'Narendra-Mandal', as the Chamber was called, furthermore, was also recognition of the rights claimed by the Princes to have a voice in

the Councils of the Empire and to participate in the discussion on 'questions affecting the state as a whole, and pertaining to the states as well as British India.¹²

Among the recommendations with regard to the States in the Montague-Chelmsford Report, the Government gave top priority to the proposal for the formation of a Council of Princes. The question was referred to the local Governments, political officers, and the Princes for their opinion. While a large number of states favoured the formation of the Chamber of Princes, certain big states like Hyderabad, Mysore, Indore and Udaipur were opposed to the idea. They feared that such a council would not enable the bigger states to exercise 'legitimate influence in the Assembly¹³ and that its deliberations and decisions would 'contravene the essential precepts that each prince is a sovereign who is entitled to conduct his business direct with the British Government, without the intervention of Indian States or of any Legislative Assemblies of British India.¹⁴ Some of the local Governments chose to echo the voice of the Indian Princes with whom they were connected.

The Lieutenant Governor of the Punjab, along with certain Political Officers like W. E. Meyer, C. R. Lowndes and C. H. H. Hill, held that such an assemblage of the Princes was not the proper machinery for co-operation between the Viceroy and the Ruling Princes. They maintained that no subject of common concern provincial and of states could be effectively discussed in a body composed of only the representatives of the Indian States. They therefore, envisaged an alternate scheme of a mixed council, composed of eleven representatives of the Provinces, thirteen delegates of the Princes, plus nine nominees of the British Government.¹⁵ According to them, such a body would provide the Princes with the full opportunity of participation in discussions on matters of all India concern besides being an effective means of establishing co-operation between the Viceroy and the Indian Princes.¹⁶

However, despite this criticism by certain states and political officers, most of the states as well as the British Government seemed to favour the idea of the formation of a Council of Princes.¹⁷ This is evident from the recommendations of the Mont-Ford report as well as from the reaction of the conference of Ruling Princes and Chiefs, which met at Delhi in January 1919. The conference unanimously supported the suggestion for the formation of a Council of Princes.¹⁸ It agreed with the Mont-Ford Report that only those Rulers who enjoyed full powers of internal administration should be admitted to the

Chamber of Princes as its members.¹⁹ It also recommended that the Rulers of the States enjoying a dynastic salute of 11 Rulers who had full and unrestricted powers of civil and criminal to 13 guns be granted full powers of internal administration and that the jurisdiction in their states and the power to make their own laws be termed the 'Sovereign Princes'.²⁰ The Government of India consented to the removal of the restrictions imposed on certain States enjoying a dynastic salute of 11 to 13 guns but thought that "the application of the term Sovereign Princes' to a select class of 'Rulers would be inappropriate since, on the one hand, it would suggest that they possessed complete sovereign powers which was not the case and, on the other hand, it would imply that the powers exercised by Rulers in the lower class were not sovereign powers-a theory which would excite much justifiable indignation."²¹

In his inaugural speech in the Conference of Ruling Princes and Chiefs held in Nov 1919, Lord Chelmsford announced the intention of the Government of India and His Majesty's Government to call into being a permanent Chamber of Princess,²² which would be a consultative and not an executive body.²³ He made it clear that "the direct transaction of Business between the Government of India and any state will not be prejudiced by the institution of the Chamber."²⁴

The Composition of the Chamber

Lord Chelmsford, with the full concurrence of the British Government, also suggested that the Chamber should be composed of (a) States, the Rulers of which enjoyed permanent dynastic salutes Of 11 guns (b) States, the Rulers of which enjoyed permanent dynastic salutes of 9 guns and had full or practically full internal powers and (c) Such other 9 guns salutes as might be deemed fit by the Government of India for the grant of requisite internal powers.²³ It was also suggested by him that even smaller states which did not enjoy full powers of internal administration be granted representation on the Chamber.²⁴ While the conference readily agreed to the first suggestion, many Rulers present in the conference were opposed to the admission of the smaller states to the Chamber. The question was referred to a committee of Princes but it failed to come to an agreement.

Consequently, it was resolved that a few representatives of the smaller states could be admitted to the Chamber of Princes after its formation on the recommendation of a

special committee which would be formed subsequently for the purpose. The committee's recommendations accepted by the Chamber of Princess at its first session in 1921 after a heated debate, provided for the inclusion of 12 members, representing in matters that affect those territories jointly with British India or with the freely in matters relating to the territories of Indian states generally, and rest of my Empire. It will have no concern with the internal affairs of individual states or their Rulers or with the relations of individual states to my Government, while the existing rights of the states and their freedom of action will be in no way prejudiced or imposed."²⁵

The Chamber was, thus, essentially an advisory body to be consulted the Viceroy on matters of common concern to Indian States an organised forum where consultations with the Viceroy could be had but offered itself as an agency through which the Princes could place their legitimate demands before the Paramount Power and raise their voice in protest against any encroachment on their rights and prerogatives. Besides, the Chamber offered itself as a medium through which, at least Occasionally, attempts could be made to foster better understanding of and mutual co-operation for the solution of problems pertaining to British India as well as Indian States. Lastly, the Chamber, as the sole organisation of the Rulers, represented the Princes interests' at all important conferences which dealt with matters relating to both Indians as well as Empire.

The Chamber of Princes was an innovation in British policy towards their autocratic collaborators and formally ended the earlier practice of isolation. This body would be a vehicle, by which some princes could weave alliances among their peers, lobby with British officials, acquire some deliberative experience, and maintain constitutional negotiations. It was a timid solution to a complex problem required bolder initiatives. Moreover, Delhi had carefully limited its structure and functions, and princely rivalries and concern for izzat had reduced its representative-ness and potential effectiveness.²⁶

The proposal of forming an Imperial advisory council of territorial magnates of British India and ruling chiefs failed to get through because some of the important Princes disliked the idea of sitting together with the British Indian magnates. However the efforts in the direction did not stop. Neither Indian state could be kept isolated from each other for long as desired by Morley, the secretary of state, and nor was it possible to make them function as a counter poise to the Indian National Congress as desired by Minto.²⁷

In pursuance of this recommendation the Chamber of Princes came into existence. It was inaugurated by the Duke of Connaught, on behalf of the King-Emperor in the Dewan-i-Aam of the Red Fort in Delhi. The Chamber was to be deliberative, consultative and advisory body.²⁸ The Viceroy was to be its President and the members were to elect annually a Chancellor and a Pro-Chancellor from among themselves. Some important states like Hyderabad and Mysore kept out from the Chamber. Maharaja Ganga Singh of Bikaner was elected its first Chancellor, and naturally leading role.²⁹ In the Chamber medium-sized states were in majority and enjoyed dominating position.³⁰

Ten states from Rajputana Alwar, Bharatpur, Bikaner, Bundi, Dholpur, Jaisalmer, Jhalawar, Jodhpur, Kishangarh and Kota attended the first session and the number remained a record not to be surpassed in future sessions of the Chamber.³¹

So the Chamber of Princes was essentially an advisory body to be consulted by the Viceroy on matters of common concern for Indian states and the British provinces. It was a forum where the Princes could hold consultations with the Viceroy and ventilate their grievances to the British Government.³²

The rules and regulations regarding the composition, quorum, elections and functions of the Standing Committee of the Chamber of Princes were framed in its meeting of February 1921. The work of codifying the political practices and the usages was also entrusted to this Committee. It maintained a close liaison with the Political Department and discussed various issues. The decisions regarding the representatives of the smaller states and minor Rulers at the Chamber were taken. The term 'Narendra Mandal' as the vernacular designation of the Chamber of Princes was adopted.³³

The powers of the Chamber were limited in their scope. They were even more restricted by the powers accorded to the Crown Representative. The Viceroy, as the Presiding officer of the Chamber, held the key position. He was to preserve order and decide all points of order. In fact, he controlled the proceedings of the Chamber. The Chancellor presided over the meeting in the absence of the Viceroy. The Chancellor was elected by the Chamber and also spokesman of the Princes. He was a liaison officer between the Government of India and the Princes. He controlled the routine work of the Chamber. The Pro-Chancellor was to officiate as Chancellor in case of a casual vacancy. He was ex-officio member of the Standing Committee and was to be elected every year.³⁴

The most important organ of the Chamber was the Standing Committee which had its tenure from session to session. Initially it had five members, four of them representing the four divisions of Bombay, Central India, Rajputana and the Punjab, the Chancellor being the fifth one. But later on from time to time the number of its members was increased. The leadership in the committee remained with the medium- sized states, the representatives of which were dynamic and influential. The Standing Committee, consisting of the most active and prominent members of the Chamber, played a significant role In the Chamber's affairs.

The Chamber of Princes met formally as well as informally. Its meetings were held in camera till 1928 but after 1929 its formal meetings were thrown open to the public. Informal meetings, which continued to be closed sessions, were held on the eye of formal sessions.³⁵

The Chamber took up issues of quite wide range. Broadly, these may be divided into three main categories: (I) personal, (II) issues of all India Paramount Power and inter-state questions which were decided by the nature and (III) those relating to the Indian States vis-a-vis the Paramount Power.³⁶

The Chamber could create an atmosphere of solidarity and unity in the princely order but it did not always succeed in asserting itself. The Foreign Political Department acted very slowly. This is evident from the fact that between 1921 and 1930 only 10 of its 23 resolutions were accepted by the Political Department." The effectiveness of the Chamber depended largely on the attitude of the Viceroy and on the unity of the Princes. When Lord Reading took up a stiff attitude on the question of the Paramountcy and political practice, the Chamber could not make much headway in settling them. On the other hand, Lord Irwin's sympathetic attitude made the Chamber more active and vigorous.³⁷

Despite limitations under which the Chamber had to work, it became strong force which the British Government and statesmen had to reckon with. It was the sole organisation representing the princely order.

REFERENCES

1. Phadnis, Urmila; Towards the Integration of the Indian States, P. 24
2. Ibid, P. 119
3. F.P.D. No.11-16, Secret, January 1920, NAI, New Delhi
4. A Consideration of the Evolution of Political Relationship between the Crown and the States-A Memorandum, P.42.
5. Srivastava; Ram Sahai, Maharaja Ganga Singh Centenary, Vol. Page 9
6. Foreign and Political Department, Proceedings. No.296-496, December 1877, Part-II, NAI.
7. Foreign and Political Department, Proceedings., No. 296-496, December 1877, Part-II, NAI.
8. Rawlinson, H.G., The British Achievements in India, a survey, P.138
9. Vyas, R.P.; Adhunik Rajasthan Ka Vrahat Itihas, P. 9
10. Ibid.
11. Panikker, K.M., His Highness the Mahraja of Bikaner, PP.141-46.
12. Proceedings of the meeting of the Chamber of Princes, February 1921, P. 327, Rajasthan State Archives, Bikaner.
13. Phadnis; op. cit., P. 24
14. Proceedings of the Conference of Ruling Princes and Chiefs held at Delhi on the 30th Oct 1916, 5 Nov 1917, 20 Jan 1919 and 3 Nov 1919. (Confidential) P. 483
15. Foreign and Political Department, No.11-16, Secret Reforms, June 1920, NAI.
16. Ibid
17. All the states in U.P., The Punjab Hill States, States in Central India and many States of Rajputana favoured the idea of the formation of a Council of Princes.
18. Proceeding of the Conference of the Ruling Princes and Chiefs, n- 3,655.
19. Ibid, 453.
20. Ibid

21. Menon V.P.: The Story of the Integration of the Indian States, P. 17, Proceedings of the conference of the Ruling Princes and Chiefs, n-3, 587.
22. Ibid 590.
23. Ibid
24. Salutes are meant universally to indicate the status of Rulers, the highest class being entitled to 21 salutes. A table of salutes was drawn up in 1857 and published in 15th boon modified since then by additional grants and advancements". Quoted the Government of India, P. 69
25. Proceedings of The Chamber of Princes, 1921-28, n-1, 18
26. Barbara N Ramusack; The Princes of India, P. 93
27. Phadnis, op. cit., P.20
28. Prog. Chamber of Princes 1921-28, No.1, 18; Phadnis, op. Cit., P.28.; Raghubir Singh, Op. Cit. PP. 75-76
29. Jain, M. S.; Concise History of Modern Rajasthan, P. 157
30. Phadnis, Op. Cit., PP.27-28
31. Jain; op. cit., P. 155
32. The leader, 18 May 1920, News Paper Cutting, File No. 30/1925, Rajasthan State Archives, Bikaner
33. Jain; op. cit., P. 159
34. Phadnis; op. cit., P. 29
35. "Phadnis; op. cit., PP. 27-28
36. Ibid, PP. 219-20.
37. Ibid, PP. 36-37